

Condensation of Acetonedicarboxylic Acid with Phenols and Phenolic Ethers. Part I. Formation of β -Substituted Glutaconic Acids.

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Condensation of phenols with β -ketonic acids or esters takes place in the *ortho*-position to the hydroxyl group resulting in the formation of coumarins and chromones.*

During the synthesis of coumaryl-4-acetic acid from phenol, (Limaye, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 159) the formation of a dicarboxylic acid as a by-product was observed which was thought to belong to the *para*-series. This observation has since been confirmed, a modified process giving better yield worked out and the reaction extended to phenolic ethers, anisole and *o*-cresol methyl ether, by Limaye and Dixit (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1930, p. 167). That the condensation takes place in the *para*-position with respect to the hydroxyl group is proved by the fact that the products on oxidation give known *para*-substituted acids. Thus phenol, when condensed with acetonedicarboxylic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid gives a dicarboxylic acid, $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$, the methyl ether of which is identical with the product directly obtained from anisole and gives anisic acid on oxidation.

As previous workers had not observed the formation of *para*-substituted products in this type of condensation, stress was laid at first on this aspect of the reaction. But the isolation of the dicarboxylic acids opens out a new field of investigation, since these acids can be looked upon as β -substituted glutaconic acids.

Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1606) had tried to obtain glutaconic acids of the *ortho*-series by the hydrolysis of the corresponding coumarinacetic acids but he was not able to isolate such acids in the free state except in the case of the product from β -naphthol, since these acids reverted to the coumarin structure by the

* For a list of references *vide* Sen and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 467; also Naik, Desai and Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 801.

loss of water. But as the process now developed gives acids substituted in the *para*-position, the conversion to coumarinacetic acids is obviated.

The great interest attaching to the constitution of glutaconic acids in general and the ready availability of these acids by the new method, as compared to the difficulties mentioned by Bland and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 856) have led us to undertake their further investigation.

In the present paper evidence has been recorded to show that the dibasic acid from anisole, which might be taken as typical of this series of acids, has really the constitution of a β -substituted glutaconic acid. Thus the acid from anisole (I) gives, by loss of carbon dioxide, the known *p*-methoxyisopropylenebenzene (III) (Behal and Tiffeneau, *Compt. rend.*, 1901, **132**, 561). It also gives an anhydride (II) and resembles the well-known β -phenylglutaconic acid in properties.

Moreover, semicarbazide hydrochloride has been found to react with the anhydrides of β -substituted glutaconic acids for the first time. However as there are difficulties in ascribing a semicarbazone structure to these derivatives, which seem to be additive products, work is in progress to elucidate their real constitution. The action of acetic anhydride on these glutaconic acids is also being studied in detail. The results so far obtained, which lead us to reconsider the structure of an hydroxy anhydride assigned by Thorpe and his co-workers to the anhydrides of β -substituted glutaconic acids, to account for their ready titratability with alkalis, apparently as monobasic acids, and their reaction with ferric chloride, will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β-4-Methoxyphenylglutaconic Acid.—To the acetonedicarboxylic acid mixture prepared from 25 g. of citric acid and 40 c.c. of pure concentrated sulphuric acid, after the method of Dey and Row (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 112), 10 c.c. of anisole are added. The flask is allowed to stand at the room temperature (25°) for two hours, after which the contents are poured in about 150 c.c. of water. The crystalline precipitate which separates is washed with cold water and crystallized from boiling water. It is then further purified by conversion into the barium salt and its subsequent decomposition with dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid thus obtained (about 2 g.) melts at 176° (decomp.) and is insoluble in benzene. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 5.1; equi. wt., 118. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 61.0; H, 5.1 per cent., equi. wt., 118).

Anhydride of β-4-Methoxyphenylglutaconic Acid.

(a) *By heating*.—The acid (I) is heated in an oil-bath at 180° for half an hour. The product is crystallized from benzene; m.p. 160°. It titrates as a monobasic acid with alkali and in alcoholic solution, gives with ferric chloride, a greenish-blue coloration which disappears on keeping. (Found: C, 66.0; H, 4.5; equi. wt., 217. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.6 per cent., equi. wt., 218).

(b) *By acetic anhydride*.—The acid (I) (5 g.) is boiled with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) for five minutes and the solution is allowed to cool. The crystals which separate are filtered, washed with dry ether and recrystallised from benzene, m. p. 160° and are identical with the above compound.

p-Methoxyisopropylenebenzene (II).

(a) *By dry distillation with lime*.—The dibasic acid (I) is heated with lime in a flask with a side tube. A small quantity of liquid distils over which, after steam distillation, gives a white solid melting at 32.5° (yield 10-15%.) (Found: C, 81.2; H, 8.0. $C_{10}H_{12}O$ requires C, 81.1; H, 8.1 per cent.).

(b) *By boiling with mineral acid*.—The acid (I) (5 g.) is boiled with 30 c.c. of 10% hydrochloric acid for 15 minutes and then subjected to steam distillation when a solid melting at 33° passes over.

The decarboxylated product obtained in both the above processes was identical with *p*-methoxyisopropylenebenzene (Behal and

Tiffeneau, *loc. cit.*) which was prepared from ethyl anisate and methyl magnesium iodide (Klages, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3995). The same compound was also prepared for identification by heating β -methyl-*p*-methoxycinnamic acid with lime.

The Acid-Ester of the Dibasic Acid, (I).—The anhydride (III) (1 g.) and 5 c.c. of absolute alcohol are boiled for five hours under reflux. The excess of alcohol is driven off on a water-bath. The residue is dissolved in ether and the ethereal solution is extracted with sodium carbonate solution. On acidifying the alkaline extract a white product separates which on crystallisation from water melts at 126-27°. (Found: equi. wt., 263. $C_{14}H_{16}O_5$ requires equi. wt., 264).

Semianilide of β -4-Methoxyphenylglutaconic Acid.

(a) *From the anhydride.*—The anhydride (III) (1 g.) is dissolved in 40 c.c. of warm benzene and 0.5 g. of aniline added. After a few seconds a precipitate begins to separate and increases in volume on keeping. The reaction is completed by warming on the water-bath. On cooling the precipitate is filtered and exactly neutralized with alkali. The clear solution is warmed and a slight excess of barium chloride solution is added. The small quantity of precipitate which separates is filtered off and the filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The semianilide separates as a white precipitate (1 g.) and is crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 89-190° (decomp.). (Found: C, 69.2; H, 5.6; equi. wt., 309. $C_{18}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 69.4; H, 5.5 per cent., equi. wt., 311).

(b) *From the dibasic acid, (I).*—The acid (10 g.) is heated with aniline (4.5 g.) on a water-bath for two hours. The resulting mass is washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the residue purified as in (a); m. p. 190° (decomp.). The semianilide is readily convertible into the anil by heating.

Anil of β -4-Methoxyphenylglutaconic acid.

It can be prepared—

(a) By boiling 1 g. of the acid with 2 c.c. of aniline for 10 minutes.

(b) By heating 1 g. of the acid with 1.25 g. aniline in an oil-bath at 140° for five hours (yield 0.8 g.).

(c) By heating the semianilide of the acid at 200° for one hour.

The resinous mass obtained in each case is washed with dilute hydrochloric acid or ether and then rapidly recrystallised first from

alcohol or glacial acetic acid and then from benzene ; m. p. ,204-5° (Found : C, 73·6 ; H, 5·0; equi. wt., 292·5. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 73·7; H, 5·1, equi. wt., 293 per cent.).

Action of Semicarbazide Hydrochloride on the Anhydrides of β -Substituted Glutaconic Acids.

(a) β -4-Methoxyphenylglutaconic acid anhydride (0·5 g.) is dissolved in 30 c.c. of alcohol and 5 c.c. of 10% semicarbazide hydrochloride solution added. The mixture is well shaken and allowed to stand for a few hours. The white crystalline precipitate which separates is collected and recrystallised from alcohol ; m. p. 208·9° (decomp.).

(b) β -Phenylglutaconic anhydride (0·5 g.) gives under identical conditions a crystalline compound, m.p. 193°.

Both these products are readily titratable with alkali and the equivalents found indicate an addition of a semicarbazide molecule to the anhydride.

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